

ELECTRO-HYDRODYNAMIC ANALOGOUS SIMULATION OF PRESSURE CONTROL

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Abstract

An electronic analog model has been developed to simulate the compressor pressure control process. The model is a hybrid system using a real frequency inverter. The dynamics of the process in real time for different analog models of the hydrodynamic structure of the compressor pressure line have been studied. A data acquisition computer system has been used to record the parameter values during the simulation process. The pressure control simulation is carried out efficiently, the response to disturbances is adequate, and in the case of a correctly selected time scale, the model results can be transferred to a real system.

Keywords: Simulation, electrohydrodynamic analogy, electronic model, pressure control, frequency inverter.

During imitative modeling (simulation) of objects, the similarity between the object and its model is expressed by isomorphism: there must be a clear correspondence between the components of the object and the model, while maintaining the ratio and interaction between the elements [1].

The electro-hydrodynamic analogy (EHA) modeling method is based on the isomorphism of the mathematical description of electrical and hydrodynamic processes [2], namely: the analogy of the amount of substance (mass, volume) is electric charge, the analogy of flow is electric current, the analogy of pressure is electric voltage, the analogy of the capacity (volume) of the reservoir is electric capacitance. The balances of the branches and nodes of the flows correspond to Kirchhoff's law, the models of hydrodynamic machines

(pumps, compressors) are represented by sources of electric current and voltage, including machine generators. Various, mainly two-pole electrical devices with linear or nonlinear volt-ampere characteristics are used as hydraulic resistance models - resistors, diodes, Zener diodes, dynistors, etc. Electronic sensors, transistor circuits, operational amplifiers, ready-made functional electronic modules are used. Processes can be modeled on the desired time scale, including in real time mode, as a result it becomes possible to use the parameters determined in a result of the simulation of automatic process regulation in real process control systems.

Fig.1 shows a schematic diagram of a technological device where pressure is regulated in the buffer volume S1.

Fig.1. Pressure control P&ID drawing in buffer volume S1

A primitive/typical method [3] of regulating the absolute pressure measured by the pressure transmitter PT12 involves regulating the backflow from the compressor's discharge side to the suction side using the valve PV12. In this case, a significant part of the compressor's energy is wasted, the compressor wear is high, and its resource is reduced.

The alternative-progressive control contour is also shown in Fig. 1. The pressure signal from the transmitter PT12 is supplied to the controller PC12, the regulating effect of which, through the frequency inverter PY12 (Variable Frequency Drive – VFD), changes the rotational frequency of the compressor P12 motor and maintains the set pressure value. In typical frequency

inverters, the PID algorithm for regulating the target parameter (pressure, flow) is already implemented, PC12:PY12 is a combined block. For this purpose, the WK600D series frequency inverter [4] was selected.

Fig. 2 shows the electronic simulation scheme of the above-described task. The scheme uses both single electronic components and ready-made typical functional modules, which are commonly used in control systems and perform similar functions to those in the electronic model. The electrical parameters of the model correspond to specific physical quantities, and some of them are completely identical to the signals used in the control system, both qualitatively and quantitatively. The electronic model consumes little power,

is compact, can be easily placed on a desk, and can be easily transported.

The scheme depicts a hybrid system, where the PID controller and the frequency converter VFD are the minimum power model WK600D-0007-M1T of the selected series, which controls the rotation frequency of the small-power asynchronous motor M1. The motor shaft (diameter 8.2 mm) rotates the shaft of the miniature DC motor M2 (diameter 2.2 mm) through a belt

transmission, and thus the gear ratio reaches 3.73. As a result, the motor M2 is a compressor model that absorbs electric charge from the buffer model (electrical capacitance C1), the current strength is analog to the gas flow. The physical essence and range of change of the regulating parameter - frequency (0-50 Hz) are identical for any model.

Fig. 2. Electronic circuit for pressure control simulation

The analog imitative value of the process parameter - pressure is the voltage on the capacitor C1, which is converted into a 4-20 mA unified signal by the CTVIB01 module and supplied to the corresponding AI2 input of the frequency inverter. The electronic model of a stable gas pressure source (such as, for example, a cylinder/pressure regulator) is an adjustable voltage source LM2596. The resistance R1 across the capacitance C1 for the nominal (Setpoint, SP) value of the voltage +1 V determines the current value of 160 μ A. The DC generator M2 will absorb the charge of the capacitor C1 and by regulating the rotation frequency of the asynchronous motor M1 connected to the generator shaft by a belt drive, the frequency converter will maintain the set voltage of 1 V. The generator test showed that for a given gear ratio of 3.73, at a nominal rotation frequency of the asynchronous motor at 2700 rpm, the voltage of the DC generator reached 3.5 V.

The electrical parameters of the model correspond to the hydrodynamic parameters of the original as follows: 1 mA \leftrightarrow 1 L/min; 1 V \leftrightarrow 1 bar; 1 mF \leftrightarrow 10 L.

The transistor circuit VT1, R2 used to correct the peculiarity of the capacitor discharge circuit in the electronic model. Unlike the process of gas compression in the device, in the electronic model of suction, it is possible to obtain a negative voltage on the capacitor C1, which loses its physical meaning for absolute pressure, and damage to the electrolytic capacitor is also possible. The VT1 transistor is closed for a negative voltage value and theoretically it becomes impossible to negatively charge the capacitor. In fact, with a significant decrease in voltage, the transistor switches to linear mode and reduces the output current, this effect qualitatively well reflects the difficulty of suction by the compressor from low-pressure gas. When selecting

gauge pressure as a modeling parameter, the base of the VT1 transistor should be provided with a negative bias voltage equivalent to atmospheric pressure.

The load circuit connected to the positive pole of the generator represents an electronic model of the load piping line, under different line structures, with load variants A, B, C indicated on the diagram. The total pressure loss in the network ΔP when the flow moves at a velocity W is generally expressed by the equation by Bernoulli's law and with influence of friction [5,6]:

$$\Delta P = (P_2 - P_1) + \rho gh + \left(1 + \lambda \frac{L}{d} + \sum_1^n \zeta\right) \frac{\rho W^2}{2} \quad (1)$$

Where $P_2 - P_1$ is the pressure difference at the end and start points of the line; ρgh - difference in level pressure by height h ; $\frac{\rho W^2}{2}$ represents the specific kinetic energy (velocity pressure) of the flow rate; L is the length of the pipeline, d is the diameter; ζ represents the local resistance coefficients.

The coefficient of friction in laminar mode is determined as:

$$\lambda = \frac{64}{Re} \quad (2)$$

Reynolds criterion:

$$Re = \frac{W d \rho}{\mu} \quad (3)$$

where μ is the coefficient of dynamic viscosity.

Considering (2) and (3), the pressure loss over the friction in the laminar regime is proportional to the flow velocity, which corresponds to Poiseuille's law:

$$\Delta P = \frac{32 L \mu W}{d} \quad (4)$$

To calculate the friction coefficient in non-laminar mode, the formula is used, taking into account the pipe wall roughness coefficient ε :

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\left\{2 \lg \left[\frac{\varepsilon}{3.7} + \left(\frac{6.81}{Re} \right)^{0.9} \right] \right\}^2} \quad (5)$$

According to equation (1), the total pressure loss in a pipeline can be generally expressed as the flow rate G :

$$\Delta P = a_0 + a_1 G + a_2 G^2 \quad (6)$$

For the electronic simulation model, respectively:

$$U = b_0 + b_1 I + b_2 I^2 \quad (7)$$

Below are the corresponding coefficients of equation (7) and their interpretation for different models of the load pipeline in the diagram shown in Fig.2.

$$\mathbf{A}: b_0=0, b_1=13600, b_2=0$$

Such a scheme implies that the pipeline resistance is determined by a linear dependence on the flow rate. This would be possible for a laminar flow regime along the entire length of the pipeline, which does not correspond to the physical meaning when the pressure is represented in absolute values - the end of the pipeline should end in absolute vacuum, although during the simulation we can consider the end of the network at point A at the junction point of R3 and R4, without delving into the hydrodynamic process occurring in area R4.

$$\mathbf{B}: b_0=1.5, b_1=6800, b_2=0$$

This scheme implies that a stable pressure is maintained at the delivery point in the T1 device. This is realistic from a physical point of view - the pressure in the device is regulated by independent control of the hydrodynamic mode. In the electronic model, the corresponding function can be realized by a Zener diode, in our case, an LED VD1 is used in its role - with a voltage drop of 1.5 V. The hydraulic resistance to the T1 device is still linear. The model also considers the presence of a buffer volume S2 on the pressure line, the electronic analogue of which is the capacitance C2. This capacitance has no significance in the stationary mode, although it affects the dynamics of regulation.

$$\mathbf{C}: b_0=1.4, b_1=2000+40+200=2240, b_2=33.13 \cdot 10^6$$

In this scheme considered the square-law component of the line resistance, which is typical for real pipelines (1). This function is electronically implemented by an active circuit - using a programmable transmitter

Jumo dTRANS T01 [7], in which an interpolation table of the square-law component is recorded. The current is measured by the voltage drop across the resistor R5, a millivolt level signal is supplied to the galvanically isolated input of the transmitter. The output standard 4-20 mA signal through the isolating diode creates the target square-law voltage support on the ballast resistor R4. In addition, the minimum output current of 4 mA causes a constant component of 0.8 V, to which is also added a voltage drop of 0.6 V on the isolating diode VD2, for a total of $b_0=1.4$ V in equation (7). In the same equation, the coefficient of the linear component is formed by the sum of the resistors R3, R4, R5. In this mode, due to the active deep feedback in the circuit, it became necessary to add a filter capacitor C3 to suppress the generator pulsations. In the circuit, it is also possible to connect the transmitter output to the R4 load using an emitter follower circuit, in which, in addition to current amplification, it is possible to reduce or eliminate the constant component b_0 caused by the minimum current due to the voltage drops on the VT2 base-emitter junction and the VD3 diode.

D: In this approach, various ways of realizing the quadratic component in the simulation model (7) were studied using a bipolar electronic component, instead of an C: active circuit, to implement the following relationship:

$$\Delta U \sim I^2 \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3 shows a circuit replacing the P4 resistor in the circuit of Fig. 2. A temperature resistance detector (RTD) is used, its temperature dependence of resistance is close to linear. Since the simulation current I is insufficient for achieving a thermal effect, its amplification is used (in the simplest way - with a transistor connected in an open collector circuit). The 1000-times amplified current I_p feeds the heating element, which transfers heat to the miniature Pt1000 temperature sensor R4, the temperature of which is practically equal to that of the heating element. The voltage drop across the base-emitter junction of the amplifying transistor must be considered when forming the constant component b_0 in equation (7).

Fig. 3. Implementation of a current-dependent variable resistance in a load line using a resistance temperature detector and an external heater

D.1: In this variant, a thermostable resistor R_p (manganin, constantan wire) is used as a heating element. Below is the theoretically expected dependence of the nonlinear component of the voltage drop across the resistor R4 on the current strength (here and in the following variant it is assumed that the heat transfer process obeys Newton's law of cooling - the heat flux

is proportional to the difference in temperature between the body surface and the environment Δt , and the heat capacity of the heating element is determined by the Joule-Lenz law):

$$R_p = \text{Const}, I_p = 1000 \cdot I$$

$$\Delta R_4 \sim \Delta t \sim R_p \cdot I_p^2 \sim I^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta U \sim I \cdot \Delta R_4 \sim I^3 \quad (10)$$

D.2: In this version, a powerful Zener diode VD_p is used as the heating element:

$$U_p = \text{Const}, I_p = 1000 \cdot I$$

$$\Delta R_4 \sim \Delta t \sim U_p \cdot I_p \sim I \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta U \sim I \cdot \Delta R_4 \sim I^2 \quad (12)$$

D.3: In this variant, the R4 resistor is replaced by a nonlinear element - a miniature incandescent lamp.

To achieve a noticeable thermal effect, the simulation current is increased by 100 times. Accordingly, the resistors in the circuit are reduced by 100 times, and to maintain the dynamic characteristics, the buffer capacitances are increased proportionally, for this purpose the so-called supercapacitors - ionistors are used. As a result, the simulation circuit takes the form shown in Fig. 4:

Fig. 4. Simulation scheme with increased current using an incandescent lamp

Accordingly, $I_p = I$; The resistance of the cold spiral of the lamp used is $R_0 = 18$ Ohm. To ensure a scale transition from option C: to proportionally change the coefficient of the linear component b_1 in equation (7), a resistance $R_3 = 4$ Ohm is used.

We determine the volt-ampere characteristic $I = f(U)$ of an incandescent lamp experimentally and approximate its nonlinear component by a power function with the desired exponent index n :

$$\Delta U \sim I \cdot \Delta R(I) \sim I^n \quad (13)$$

Table 1 presents experimental data for all three variants - D.1, D.2, D.3. Here I is the simulation current, I_p - heater current, U_1 - full voltage, U_0 - linear component of voltage, determined by the cold value of R_4 , ΔU - nonlinear component of voltage, with the power function of which we determine the exponent index n by the formula:

$$n = \frac{\lg(\Delta U_2 / \Delta U_1)}{\lg(I_2 / I_1)} \quad (14)$$

Table 1

Experimental measurement results for nonlinear loads

I, mA	I_p, A	$t, ^\circ C$	R_4, Ohm	U_1, mV	U_0, mV	$\Delta U, mV$	n
D.1							
0	0	24	1088.7	0	0	0	2.81
0.30	0.30	92	1360.3	408.1	326.6	81.5	
0.45	0.45	169	1654.0	744.3	489.9	254.4	
D.2							
0	0	24.4	1088.7	0	0	0	1.84
0.11	0.11	63.2	1248.6	137.3	119.8	17.6	
0.22	0.22	95.8	1374.9	302.5	239.5	63.0	
D.3							
0	0	24	18	0	0	0	1.99
16.7	0.0167	?	72.5	1210	301	910	
33.4	0.0334	?	126.0	4210	601	3607	
54.4	0.0544	?	183.8	10000	979	9021	

As can be seen from the table 1, the best correspondence of the quadratic dependence of the voltage ΔU to the current I ($n=1.99$) was shown by option D.3. At the same time, the quadratic component ΔU is several times greater than the linear U_0 , while for options D.1, D.2 it is the opposite. This is important, since during the simulation it is always possible to increase the linear component by sequentially switching on the re-

sistance. Most importantly, for options D.1, D.2, thermal equilibrium is established with a long delay - for tens of minutes, which is incompatible with the simulation of hydrodynamic processes. And in case D.3, the temperature of the incandescent filament of the lamp and, accordingly, the resistance and voltage drop across it are established almost instantly.

Fig. 5 shows the experimental points of the volt-ampere characteristic of the miniature incandescent

lamp CMH-50-10-2 and the approximation of the dependence by the equation:

$$U_1 = 18I + 3260I^2 \quad (15)$$

Finally, the D.3 load is selected as option D, increasing the simulation current by 100 times.

Fig. 5. Volt-ampere characteristic of the incandescent lamp CMH-50-10-2

For the simulation scheme presented in Fig. 4, the coefficients of equation (7) are determined as: $b_0=1.33$, $b_1=4+18=22$, $b_2=3260$ - where $b_0=1.33$ V is determined by the VD1 Zener diode.

Fig. 6 shows the pipeline characteristic curves on the load line of the virtual compressor (motor M2) for different types of loads: A, B, C, D. It should be noted that in case D the current on the abscissa reflects a value 100 times higher.

Fig. 6. Pipeline characteristic curves for different types of loads on the compressor pressure line

The graphs show that the result of the active formation of the nonlinear voltage C is practically identical to the voltage drop characteristic D on an lamp load, the small difference being mainly due to the difference in the values of the constant component b_0 (in case C, 1.4 V is formed with a minimum transmitter current of 4 mA and a voltage drop across the isolating diode VD2, while in case D 1.33 V is formed with a voltage drop across the Zener diode VD1).

An analog simulation modeling of automatic pressure control in the buffer volume S1 (analogous to the capacitor C1) has been carried out in real time using the above-described electronic simulation schemes.

During the simulation process, it is convenient to use a computer USB Data Acquisition Module - 10-Channel ADC 12Bit AD Sampling Module STM32F103C6T6 Analog Digital USB Interface STM32 UART Communication Analog Digital Mod-

ule [8]. The control points and the nominal voltage values at them are indicated on the diagrams. The voltage drop formed by the 4-20 mA signal supplied to the AI2 input across the input impedance of 400 Ohm which is the parameter PV for the PID control loop of the frequency inverter and the control parameter CV - the 0-

10 VDC range at the AM analog output of the frequency converter was reading.

Table 2. presents a fragment of a computer record converted into an Excel spreadsheet.

Table 2

Fragment of a computer record of a data acquisition module

Date	Time	Channel	Numerical Value	Value	Unit
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH0	2005	1.616	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH1	2185	1.760	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH2	2011	1.620	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH3	2190	1.764	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH4	0	0.000	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH5	1250	1.007	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH6	1825	1.471	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH7	2098	1.690	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH8	1975	1.591	V
24.01.2025	13:22:11	CH9	2178	1.754	V

Fig. 7 presents the results of analog simulation modeling of automatic pressure control in real time using the above-described electronic simulation schemes.

Fig.7. Results of simulation of automatic pressure control for electronic model schemes A, B, C, D

The programming codes of the frequency inverter used in the hybrid electronic circuit of the model are identical to the actually desired powerful model, and the codes determined in a result of the simulation are used on a powerful device.

Table 3 shows the codes that correspond to the task set and were determined in the simulation process on the electronic model.

Table 3

WK600 series Frequency Inverter programming codes

Function Code	Parameter name	Setting Range	Set [Default]	property
Group P0: Standard Function parameters				
P0-00	G/P type display	1: G type (constant torque load) 2: P type (variable torque load e.g. fan and pump)	1	●
P0-01	Motor 1 control mode	0 : Speed Sensorless Vector Control (SVC) 1: Speed sensor vector control (FVC) 2: Voltage/Frequency (V/F) control	2 [2, 0?]	★
P0-02	Command source selection	0: Operation panel control (LED off) 1: Terminal control (LED on) 2: Communication control (LED blinking)	0	☆
P0-03	Main frequency source X selection	0: Digital setting (non-retentive at power failure) 1: Digital setting (retentive at power failure) 2: AI1 (The factory default is the panel potentiometer, which can be switched by jumper J9) 3: AI2 4: AI3 5: Pulse setting (X5/X6) 6: Multi-reference 7: Simple PLC 8: PID 9: Communication setting	8 [4, 0?]	★
P0-10	Maximum frequency	50.00–500.00 Hz	50.00	★
P0-12	Frequency upper limit	Frequency lower limit (P0-14) to maximum frequency (P0-10)	50.00	☆
P0-14	Frequency lower limit	0.00 Hz to frequency upper limit (P0-12)	00.00	☆
P0-20	?	00.00 (20.00 for Single Phase Output)	00.00	★
Group P1: Motor 1 parameters				
P1-00	Motor type selection	0: Common asynchronous motor 1: Variable frequency asynchronous motor 2: Permanent magnetic synchronous motor (3: Single Phase Motor, 150 VAC Output) (4: Single Phase Motor, 250 VAC Output)	1	★
Group P4: Input Terminals				
P4-18	AI curve 2 minimum input	0.00 V to P4-20	1.80 (4mA) [0.00]	☆
P4-19	Corresponding setting of AI curve 2 minimum input	-100.00%–100.0%	0.00	☆
P4-20	AI curve 2 maximum input	P4-18 to 10.00 V	9.06(20mA) [10.00]	☆
P4-21	Corresponding setting of AI curve 2	-100.00%–100.0%	100.00	☆

	maximum input			
Group PA: Process Control PID Function				
PA-00	PID setting source	0: PA-01 1: AI1 2: AI2 3: AI3 4: Pulse setting (X5/X6) 5: Communication setting 6: Multi-reference	0	☆
PA-01	PID digital setting	0.0%–100.0%	10 [50]	☆
PA-02	PID feedback source	0: AI1 1: AI2 2: AI3 3: AI1 – AI2 4: Pulse setting (X5/X6) 5: Communication setting 6: AI1 + AI2 7: MAX (AI1 , AI2) 8: MIN (AI1 , AI2)	1 [0]	☆
PA-03	PID action direction	0: Forward action 1: Reverse action	1 [0]	☆
PA-04	PID setting feedback range	0–65535 This parameter is a non-dimensional unit. It is used for PID setting display (U0-15) and PID feedback display (U0-16).	1000	☆
PA-05	Proportional gain Kp1	0.0–100.0	30 [20]	☆
PA-06	Integral time Ti1	0.01–10.00s	6 [2]	☆
PA-07	Differential time Td1	0.000–10.000s	0.000	☆

"☆": The parameter can be modified when the AC drive is in either stop or running state.

"★": The parameter cannot be modified when the AC drive is in the running state.

"●": The parameter is the actually measured value and cannot be modified.

The changed values are highlighted in yellow. The process parameter setpoint SP – 10% is marked in green, which for the parameter range of the electronic model 0-10 V corresponds to 1 V (1 Bar for the selected scale of the model), and for the 4-20 mA signal supplied to the converter 5.6 mA. For the control system of the real device, it is determined by the measurement ranges of the pressure transmitter used. For example, if the transmitter measurement range are 0...4 bar abs., the output signal is 4-20 mA, to maintain 1 bar abs. the setpoint (SP) should be set to 25%.

The developed electronic analog model allows the study and analysis of the dynamics of hydrodynamic processes and their control in real time, the determination of optimal control parameters, and the transfer of results to a real system.

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